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Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction, And the Mental Health of Work-From-Home Employees: A Mixed Method Approach

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Abstract

The study investigates various aspects of the work-from-home experience, combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies to provide a comprehensive understanding. The quantitative phase reveals that work-from-home employees exhibit high levels of self-efficacy, above-average levels of job satisfaction, and above-average mental health. There is a very low correlation between self-efficacy and mental health ($r=.24$), and the relationship is significant ($p=.005$). However, there is a very low correlation between self-efficacy and mental health ($r=-.12$), and the relationship is not significant ($p=.164$). In the qualitative phase, the lived experience of work-from-home employees is explored, highlighting the adaptability of their work environment, time efficiency, and the value of effective management. Challenges include social isolation and technical issues. Coping mechanisms involve breathing techniques, mindfulness, and social engagement. The integration of quantitative and qualitative data suggests actionable strategies, including training webinars on technical issue optimization, promoting open communication between employees and supervisors, and implementing stress management programs. The study's findings contribute to understanding the complexities of the work-from-home experience and offer practical recommendations for enhancing the well-being and effectiveness of work-from-home employees.

Keywords: *self-efficacy, job satisfaction, mental health, lived experiences, work-from-home employees*

Introduction

The pandemic caused tremendous changes in all parts of the world. It highlighted the significance of healthcare and responsiveness, as well as the need for workplace flexibility. Work-from-home practice has existed for years and is currently the only method for firms to continue operations and avoid disruptions. It demonstrated to businesses that a portion of their duties may be performed outside the office without harming job productivity or expenses. Specifically, employees directly experienced benefits. They were able to spend more time with their families and better organize their schedules by working from home. This resulted in evolving employee expectations throughout time. As a popular destination for outsourced and freelance labor, the Philippines was already familiar with working from home prior to the outbreak. More than half of Filipino workers (52%) have been working from home for years, according to a JobStreet-conducted study. During the pandemic, it reached 85 percent. Although the arrangement had a detrimental impact on the mental health of employees, over half (49%) still prefer working from home (Estrellado, 2023). Furthermore, based on Memon et al. (2022), poor mental health is caused by pressures at work. The vast variety of reported stressors illustrates the severity and complexity of the tough work conditions experienced by employees, such as unanticipated workloads, shifting deadlines, and increased work. This indicates that the existing burden of work at home employees is not a problem; rather, problems arise when additional work is assigned to them. Since employment is no longer limited to a 9-to-5-day, work-from-home environments also affect work schedules. When given the option to work-from-home, employees are frequently required to put in longer hours.

Meanwhile, Stangrecka and Bagieński (2021) stated that, positive mental health at the workplace is a crucial part of the management of modern organizations. The development of positive mental health allows for the betterment of the work environment and has a favorable impact on employees and the results of their work commitments. Especially in times of unanticipated adjustments and reorganization caused by important events such as the pandemic, the importance of excellent mental health at work increases. As a result of the pandemic's effects, employee anxiety, stress, and risk perceptions have substantially increased. New factors such as health and life threats, numerous regulations and guidelines resulting from the pandemic state, isolation and lack of social support, disturbed work-home balance, inadequate physical activity lowering overall stress resistance, and a disturbed work-home balance all contributed to stress. Thus, it is crucial to know the mechanisms that support mental health outside of the workplace.

The study of Singh et al. (2019), demonstrates a positive relationship between self-efficacy and mental health at work. Moreover, the data suggest that the relationship between self-efficacy and mental health in the workplace was stronger among executives with a high level of sustainability practices and vice versa. However, in the study of Mata and Tarroja (2022), employees reported a moderate degree of emotional weariness, they also reported a high level of mental health, even in the absence of self-efficacy as a moderating variable. Emotional fatigue and self-efficacy are independent determinants of mental health. The results indicate that self-efficacy is not a mediator of emotional tiredness and mental health; thus, self-efficacy does not attenuate the link between emotional tiredness and mental health.

The COVID-19 outbreak poses a significant threat to the employees' emotional and mental health. According to the study of Nodoushan (2022), the study found a correlation between job satisfaction and mental health in a way that is significantly associated with COVID-19 driven anxiety. However, as per the study of Bellmann and Hübler (2021), the shift to the new normal was difficult, and individuals

must accept it in order to determine whether working from home improves or degrades job satisfaction and mental health. Thus, the result revealed that job satisfaction has a negative relationship on mental health. Moreover, this study investigates the level of self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and mental health among work-from-home employees and examines the existing relationship between the said variables. Thus, to explore the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms during the work-from-home setup. The findings of this study will be used as the basis for the Mental Health Program among work-from-home employees.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the self-efficacy, job satisfaction and their relationship to the mental health of work-from-home employees. It sought to explore the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of work-from-home employees. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How may the respondents' self-efficacy be described?
2. How may the respondents' job satisfaction be defined in terms of:
 - 2.1. general satisfaction;
 - 2.2. intrinsic and;
 - 2.3. extrinsic?
3. How may the respondents' mental health be defined in terms of:
 - 3.1. anxiety;
 - 3.2. depression;
 - 3.3. loss of behavioral control/ emotional control;
 - 3.4. general positive affect;
 - 3.5. emotional ties; and
 - 3.6. life satisfaction?
4. Is there a significant relationship between self-efficacy and mental health of a work-from-home employee?
5. Is there a significant relationship between Job satisfaction and the mental health of a work-from-home employee?
6. What are the lived experiences of work-from-home employees?
7. What are the challenges faced by work-from-home employees?
8. What are the coping mechanisms of work-from-home employees?
9. Based on the findings of the study what program can be made?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method sequential explanatory design to determine the relationship between self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and the mental health of work-from-home employees. Mixed-methods research combines both quantitative and qualitative research techniques. Combining the benefits of both approaches, mixed methods aim to provide a more comprehensive understanding than what could be achieved through a purely quantitative or qualitative study alone (George, 2022).

The primary goal of the sequential explanatory design is to interpret and explain quantitative data with qualitative data collection and analysis, (Muhaimin, 2019). In the first phase, the quantitative study employed a correlational research design. According to Bhandari (2021), a correlational research design examines the correlations between variables without the researcher influencing or controlling them. The research utilized a questionnaire to measure the respondent's self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and mental health. The quantitative data gathered were subjected to statistical analysis through correlational analysis to assess if there existed a relationship between the research variables.

In addition, the second phase employs Heideggerian phenomenology to investigate the lived experiences of participants. Based on Kelly et al. (2023), The phenomenology of Martin Heidegger offers qualitative researchers trying to interpret the lived experience of study respondents with methodological guidelines.

This study also employed Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which is based on a modified Van Kaam strategy popularized by Moustakas. Moustakas introduced seven modifications to Van Kaam's method, including horizontalization, reduction and elimination, categorization and thematization of invariant constituents, application and validation, construction of the individual textural description, construction of the individual structural description, and composite description (Galinha-de-Sá & Velez, 2019).

Furthermore, the outcomes of both the qualitative and quantitative phases were summarized and analyzed by discussing the extent to which and the way the quantitative results generalize or support the qualitative findings.

Participants

The first phase of this investigation will include the participants with the research instruments. In addition, the second phase of this study will consist of in-depth interviews among each respondent.

In the first phase, the convenience sampling technique was utilized, in which sample units were selected depending on their accessibility

to the researcher (Nikolopoulou, 2022). This study used Raosoft to identify the margin of error or sample size, providing comprehensive explanations of the statistics and the algorithm that underpinned the calculations. The researchers only required a sample size of 136 respondents from a population of 208 individuals who work from home.

In the second phase of the research procedure, the researcher also used purposive sampling techniques. The selected respondents underwent a qualitative method, with interviews conducted to determine their experiences and challenges as work-from-home employees and matched the following inclusion criteria: (1) Working-from-home; (2) living alongside family; (3) 18 to 30 years old; (4) work-from-home employee that work in Manila; (5) at least have at least 1 year of experience working from home and; (6) has a low mean score on the instrument that was given.

Exclusion criteria for work-from-home employees may include: (1) Working on site; (2) living independently; (3) 17 below or 31 years old and above; (4) work-from-home employee that work outside Manila; (5) don't have at least 1 year of experience working from home; (6) has a high mean score on the instrument that was given.

Instruments

General Self-Efficacy Scale

The General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) of Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1979) measures general self-efficacy. The measure was designed to test a general feeling of perceived self-efficacy with the intention of predicting adaptability after experiencing a variety of stressful life events and coping with daily problems. It is composed of ten components with Cronbach's alphas ranging between 0.76 and 0.90. It is assessed using a rating system of 1 to 4, and the final score is determined by adding up all the individual scores (Tus, 2020).

Likert Scale	Mean	Interpretation
1	0.01-0.99	Low
2	1.00-1.99	Below Average
3	2.00-2.99	Above Average
4	3.00-4.00	High

Minnesota job satisfaction scale

According to Parombean et al. (2023), the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale is a 20-item, 5-point Likert scale that measures the intrinsic and extrinsic components of job satisfaction experienced by individuals. Weiss et al. (1977) created the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale to measure job satisfaction. It is utilized to assess employee job satisfaction. The Minnesota Work Satisfaction Scale's Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient has been determined by Baycan to be 0.77. Intrinsic Satisfaction and extrinsic Satisfaction are the subdimensions of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. intrinsic job satisfaction includes success, acknowledgment, approval, the job itself, responsibilities, and opportunities for progress. The intrinsic satisfaction score is computed by dividing the sum of the intrinsic factor scores (1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 15, 16, and 20) by 12. Extrinsic satisfaction comprises job-related elements such as institutional policy, type of management and supervision, relationships with coworkers and employees, working conditions, and compensation. The extrinsic satisfaction score is calculated by dividing the total score from the extrinsic factor items (5, 6, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, and 19) by 8. Intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction components are included in the calculation of General satisfaction (Danaci and Koc, 2019).

Likert Scale	Mean	Interpretation
1	1.00-1.80	Low
2	1.81-2.60	Below Average
3	2.61-3.40	Average
4	3.41-4.20	Above Average
5	4.21 - 5.00	High

Mental Health Inventory

According to Parombean et al. (2023) the MHI-38 exhibited both psychological wellbeing and psychological distress. The MHI-38 and its components, psychological well-being ($\alpha = 0.894$) and psychological distress ($\alpha = 0.952$), exhibited high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.892$). The results of the confirmatory factor analysis indicated a satisfactory fit (RMSEA = 0.048, CFI = 0.945, NFI = 0.908, TLI = 0.929). Psychological well-being had a moderate correlation with the Satisfaction with Life Scale ($r = 0.469, p = 0.00$) and positive affect ($r = 0.448, p = 0.00$), but a negative correlation with the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale ($r = 0.230, p = 0.00$). Psychological distress had a strong correlation with the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale ($r = 0.910, p = 0.00$) and negative affect ($r = 0.857, p =$

Likert Scale	Mean	Interpretation
1	1.00-1.80	Low
2	1.81-2.60	Below Average
3	2.61-3.40	Average
4	3.41-4.20	Above Average
5	4.21 - 5.00	High

0.00), but a negative correlation with the Satisfaction with Life Scale ($r = 0.556$, $p = 0.00$).

Likert Scale	Mean	Interpretation
1	1.00-1.83	Low
2	1.84-2.66	Below Average
3	2.67-3.49	Average
4	3.50-4.32	Above Average
5	4.33 - 5.15	High
6	5.16 -5.98	Very High

Qualitative Research Instrument

Semi-Structured Interview Guide

A semi-structured interview is a form of data collection that involves asking questions within a preset theme framework. Nevertheless, the questions are neither organized nor phrased. Semi-structured interviews in research are frequently qualitative in design, As said by George (2022). The content of the questions in the interview guide has been validated to establish its reliability. Validation was performed by a trained professional. According to the research topic and study variables, all results were reviewed and validated. After the instrument was validated, revisions and alterations were made prior to interviewing the 15 participants for the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Primarily, the focus of the study was to explore self-efficacy and job satisfaction and their relationship to the mental health of work-from-home employees. The first phase in the research process involved the quantitative phase, followed by the second design, which was the qualitative design. Once the panelists approved the study, the researchers sent a consent form through a written letter to the research adviser for permission to start gathering data from the respondents.

Web-based resources were used to classify articles or research journals through internet searches using Google, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate. This was done by searching specific journals that had published quantitative and qualitative research regarding self-efficacy and job satisfaction and their relationship to the mental health of work-from-home employees.

To gather the necessary information for the first phase of the study, the quantitative phase, a specified number of work-from-home employees completed the necessary research questionnaires: General Self-Efficacy Scale, Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, and Mental Health Inventory. Once all scales were administered, the responses were scored and interpreted in accordance with the scoring guide for each measure.

After a week, with the informed consent of the research participants, a semi-structured interview guide validated by a professional was used to conduct comprehensive individual interviews with the research participants regarding their lived experiences, as well as a confirmation of the results of their questionnaire. The interviews were audio recorded or with written responses, then transcribed and analyzed. The collected responses were analyzed statistically using Microsoft Excel, and the results of the quantitative and qualitative phases of the research were combined to produce in-depth findings.

Procedure

In the quantitative phase, the data was tabulated and processed using Microsoft excel. the statistical techniques that will be used include:

Measure of Central Tendency (Mean).

The mean of a dataset is a statistical measure that represents the arithmetic average value of the dataset. The mean holds significance as it provides insight into the central tendency of a dataset by indicating the approximate location of the center value, Zach (2022). This was used to determine the average scores of the respondents in their general self-efficacy, job satisfaction and mental health.

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) is the most widespread method for assessing linear correlation. The coefficient of determination measures the degree and direction of the link between two variables, as stated by Turney (2022). This was used to determine the significant relationship between Self-efficacy, Job satisfaction and their relationship to mental health of work-from-home employees.

For the qualitative phase, the analysis that will be used include:

Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) focuses on lived experiences and how individuals make meaning of these experiences from the perspective of their personal and social environments. Beyond summarizing what others have said, the IPA attempts to comprehend what the experience is like from the person's perspective. Rather than prescribing specific steps that must be taken. This was used to investigate the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of work-from-home employees, (Smith and Nizza,2022).

Moreover, qualitative data were compared to quantitative data to assess how well they matched up. This process helped ensure that the qualitative data were reliable and accurate.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher ensured that participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and participants had the option to withdraw at any moment. This was done to guarantee that volunteers were not compelled to participate if it would negatively impact their physical or mental health or be otherwise burdensome. Any personally identifiable information that participants provided was strictly confidential and used only for the purposes stated in Republic Act 10173. Measures were taken to ensure that the data could not be used to identify anyone other than the researcher.

After receiving the necessary information, individuals gave their consent to participate in the study. Each participant received a permission letter explaining the key features of the study and what was expected of them, along with the researcher's contact information. Participants who agreed to participate and understood the nature of their involvement were required to sign a consent form included with the letter.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative Phase

In this phase, the focus is the numerical data and empirical measurements, with the goal of quantifying the correlation of self-efficacy, job satisfaction and mental health in work-from home employees.

The Level of Self-efficacy of Work-from-home employees

Table 1. *The Level of General Self-efficacy*

Based on the findings in Table 1, the highest mean is from indicator "I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.", with

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough	3.24	High
2. If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want.	2.90	Above average
3. It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.	2.87	Above average
4. I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events.	2.90	Above average
5. Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations.	3.24	High
6. I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.	3.49	High
7. I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities.	3.26	High
8. When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions.	3.25	High
9. If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution.	3.26	High
10. I can usually handle whatever comes my way.	3.18	High
Grand Mean	3.16	High

Legend: 0.01-1.00 = low, 1.01-1.99 = Below average, 2.00-2.99 = Above average, 3.00-4.00 = High.

a mean of 3.49, interpreted as high. Employees with self-efficacy have the capacity to influence their own reality through their actions and motivation. As a result, it increases their work-performance, and they are more inclined to perceive difficulties as possibilities for growth. (Marques, 2020). While the lowest mean is from indicator "It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.", with a mean of 2.87, interpreted as above average. Employees with self-efficacy exert a significant impact on the decisions they undertake and the objectives they establish for themselves. This led to a strong commitment to attaining those objectives. This generally results in enhanced overall performance (Khalique, 2019).

The respondent's self-efficacy obtained total mean scores is 3.16, interpreted as having a high level of self-efficacy. This shows that the work-from-home employees are resilient to stress. To support the finding the study of Phiradi et al. (2021), The policy of working from home during the pandemic will not have a negative effect on the self-efficacy of employees, so long as they perceive that their presence is significant to society and that they are included in their social circle. Working from home may physically distance individuals and isolate them from one another; yet interconnections among them, backed by social media activities, can always keep them believing that they matter, thus preventing them from losing confidence in their ability to perform their work well. However, Low self-efficacy can lead employees to either doubt their abilities or perceive tasks as more difficult than they are. This can result in employees not exerting enough effort, blaming themselves for underachievement, and ultimately losing their confidence and trust in themselves. When goals are overly ambitious, an employee's performance may suffer, which can have adverse effects on their self-efficacy and future performance. Such goals may also trigger a downward efficacy spiral. Conversely, setting goals that are too low can give a person a false sense of self-efficacy, leading to greater frustration and discouragement when they encounter more challenging tasks (Khalique, 2019).

The Level of Job Satisfaction of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 2. The level of job satisfaction

Based on the findings in Table 2, the highest mean is from indicator 20 “The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.”, with a

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Being able to keep busy all the time.	3.29	Average
2. The chance to work alone on the job.	3.83	Above average
3. The chance to do different things from time to time.	3.79	Above average
4. The chance to be “somebody” in the community.	3.61	Above average
5. The way my boss handles his/her workers.	3.51	Above average
6. The competence of my supervisor in making decisions.	3.66	Above average
7. Being able to do things that don’t go against my conscience.	3.56	Above average
8. The way my job provides for steady employment.	3.58	Above average
9. The chance to do things for other people.	4.09	Above average
10. The chance to tell people what to do.	3.65	Above average
11. The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	4.16	Above average
12. The way company policies are put into practice.	3.88	Above average
13. My pay and the amount of work I do.	3.49	Above average
14. The chances for advancement on this job.	3.75	Above average
15. The freedom to use my own judgment.	4.03	Above average
16. The chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	4.04	Above average
17. The working conditions.	3.77	Above average
18. The way my co-workers get along with each other.	3.98	Above average
19. The praise I get for doing a good job.	3.92	Above average
20. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.18	Above average
Grand Mean	3.79	Above average

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = low, 1.81-2.60 = Below average, 2.61-3.40 = Average, 3.41-4.20 Above average, 4.21 – 5.00

High

mean of 4.18, interpreted as high, employees with high level of job satisfaction demonstrate optimistic views towards their job. Their positive perception of their job is strengthened by the fact that they perceive their responsibilities as worthwhile, challenging, and rewarding. Employee satisfaction is associated with work enthusiasm and drive, which in turn increases productivity. (Omah and Obiekwe, 2019). While the lowest mean is from indicator 1 “Being able to keep busy all the time.”, with a mean of 3.29, interpreted as average. The most productive condition for a human is workflow, and interruptions kill it. Working from home is interrupted by poor internet, power outages, and noise. A mean score falling within the average range could indicate occasional disruptions or difficulties in sustaining a consistent and efficient workflow (Kos,2020).

The respondents general job satisfaction obtained total mean scores is 3.79, interpreted as having a high level of job satisfaction. In support of the findings as proven by the study of Kasemsap (2017), that the work-from-home employees are motivated and happy about their job setup. In modern companies, higher levels of job satisfaction significantly contribute to enhanced organizational productivity, decreased loss of employees, and relieved job-related stress. Job satisfaction encourages a favorable work environment and is crucial for securing increased financial gains for the organization. In contrast job dissatisfaction has the potential to create a detrimental workplace environment. Employees who are disengaged and dissatisfied may disseminate negative attitudes and behaviors, which can lead to decreased morale among their colleagues. This negative work culture can additionally contribute to reduced motivation, heightened conflict, and decreased collaboration among team members (Bonifacio, 2023).

The Level of Intrinsic Satisfaction of Work-From-home Employees

Table 3. The Level of General Self-efficacy

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Being able to keep busy all the time.	3.29	Average
2. The chance to work alone on the job.	3.83	Above Average
3. The chance to do different things from time to time.	3.79	Above Average
4. The chance to be “somebody” in the community.	3.61	Above Average
7. The way my job provides for steady employment.	3.56	Above Average
8. The chance to do things for other people.	3.58	Above Average
9. The chance to tell people what to do.	4.09	Above Average
10. The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.65	Above Average
11. The way my job provides for steady employment.	4.16	Above Average
15. The freedom to use my own judgment.	4.03	Above Average
16. The chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	4.04	Above Average
20. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.18	Above Average
Grand Mean	3.82	Above Average

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = low, 1.81-2.60 = Below average, 2.61-3.40 = Average, 3.41-4.20 Above average,

4.21 – 5.00=High

Based on the findings in Table 3, the highest mean is from indicator 20 “The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.”, with a mean of 4.18, interpreted as high. While the lowest mean is from the indicator 1 “Being able to keep busy all the time, with a mean of

3.29”, interpreted as average. The respondents intrinsic job satisfaction obtained total mean scores of 3.82, interpreted as having a high level of intrinsic satisfaction. This shows that work-from-home employees are motivated by their job.

To support the findings, the results of the study of Manzoor (2021), indicate that intrinsic rewards have a significant and positive effect on employee performance. More specifically, the research findings indicate that the relationship between intrinsic rewards and employee performance is substantially mediated by employee motivation. On the other hand, without intrinsic motivation, one is prone to losing interest in their work and falling into a spiral of inefficiency (Marinoff, 2023).

The Level of Extrinsic Satisfaction of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 4. *The Level of Extrinsic Satisfaction*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
5. The way my boss handles his/her workers.	3.51	Above Average
6. The competence of my supervisor in making decisions.	3.66	Above Average
12. The way company policies are put into practice.	3.88	Above Average
13. My pay and the amount of work I do.	3.49	Above Average
14. The chances for advancement on this job.	3.75	Above Average
17. The working conditions.	3.77	Above Average
18. The way my co-workers get along with each other.	3.98	Above Average
19. The praise I get for doing a good job.	3.92	Above Average
Grand Mean	3.75	Above Average

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = low, 1.81-2.60 = Below average, 2.61-3.40 = Average, 3.41-4.20 Above Average, 4.21 – 5.00 High

Based on the findings in Table 4, the highest mean is from indicator 5 “The way my co-workers get along with each other.”, with a mean of 3.98, interpreted as high. Based on the study of Inayat & Khan (2021), the greatest factors that influence employee satisfaction are safety and positive relationships with supervisors and colleagues; organizational commitment is significantly influenced by the nature of the job, the manner of supervision, job security, recognition, and advancement opportunities. While the lowest mean is from indicator 13 “My pay and the amount of work I do.”, with a mean of 3.49, interpreted as high. There is a widespread conviction among many individuals that compensation is an essential component of job satisfaction. This indicates that employees are more content with their contributions when they receive a competitive salary (Throat, 2022). The respondents extrinsic job satisfaction obtained total mean scores of 3.75, interpreted as having a high level of intrinsic satisfaction. This shows that work-from-home employees are satisfied in regard to their job’s salary, stability, and security.

To support the findings based on the study of Hamzah & Matkhairuddin (2022), The results reveal a statistically significant positive correlation among multiple variables, including salary and bonuses, and employees' performance. This signifies that, within the studied population, there exists a discernible relationship between the remuneration, comprising both salary and bonuses, and the performance levels of employees. This implies that a higher compensation for job roles, coupled with the provision of bonuses following one year of service, contributes to an increased likelihood of enhanced job performance among employees. extrinsic rewards have been shown to enhance employees' job satisfaction and, consequently, boost the productivity of the organization. Employees will also exhibit enhanced job performance and motivation when their employers provide superior extrinsic rewards. Positive results and a sense of accomplishment while on the job result from job satisfaction. Reward systems exert a positive influence on employee performance within an organization due to their potential for improving the work competency of the members. In contrast, an employee who lacks motivation is prone to exerting minimal effort towards work responsibilities, generating poor work, evading the workplace, and potentially quitting their position if given the chance to do so. A reduction in employee extrinsic motivation will correspondingly lead to a decrease in employee engagement (Engidaw, 2021).

The Level of Anxiety of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 5. *The Level of Anxiety*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
3. How often did you become nervous or jumpy when faced with excitement or unexpected situations during the past month?	3.81	Above average
11. How much of the time, during the past month, have you been a very nervous person?	3.76	Above average
13. During the past month, how much of the time have you felt tense or “high-strung”?	3.57	Above average
15. During the past month, how often did your hands shake when you tried to do something?	3.30	Average
25. How much have you been bothered by nervousness, or your “nerves”, during the past month?	3.47	Average
29. During the past month, how much of the time have you felt restless, fidgety, or impatient?	3.22	Average
32. During the past month, how often did you get rattled, upset, or flustered?	3.64	Above average
33. During the past month, have you been anxious or worried?	3.55	Above average
35. How often during the past month did you find yourself trying to calm down?	3.74	Above average
Grand Mean	3.56	Above average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 – 5.15, High, 5.16 -5.98 = Very High.

Based on the findings in Table 5, the highest mean is from indicator 3 “How often did you become nervous or jumpy when faced with excitement or unexpected situations during the past month?”, with a mean of 3.81, interpreted above average. Stress is experienced when the body reacts to any type of threat. These potential dangers may originate from within or without an organization. Everyone feels overwhelmed, anxious, frustrated, and alert in their presence. Moreover, while individual responses to stress may vary, the collective experience is one of increased distraction and reduced decision-making capacity (Woolf, 2022). And the lowest mean is from indicator 29 “During the past month, how much of the time have you felt restless, fidgety, or impatient?”, with a mean of 3.22, interpreted as average. Employees felt restless and exhausted because of working excessively and a lack of social interaction, which have a significant relationship with anxiety. For instance, the difficulties associated with adjusting to work-from-home, the possibility of isolation, or the lack of clarity regarding the future of work-from-home could all contribute to these emotions (Schiavo, 2021).

The respondents' anxiety obtained total mean scores of 3.56, interpreted as having an above average anxiety level. To support the finding according to Nazario (2021), Having an above average level of anxiety in the workplace can significantly affect an employee's career. Even employees who experience anxiety on the job may base their professional decisions on their anxiety. In contrast, based on the study of Hayes (2023), When anxious employees are in a state of self-management, they are more likely to develop comprehensive plans that enable them to prevent future tension by making concrete advancements towards their objectives. In a significant manner, the beneficial impacts of anxiety can enhance the potential of anxious employees.

The Level of Depression of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 6. *The Level of Depression*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
9. Did you feel depressed during the past month?	3.43	High
19. How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt downhearted and blue?	3.56	Above average
30. During the past month, how much of the time have you been moody or brooded about things?	3.50	Above average
36. During the past month, how much of the time have you been in low or very low spirits?	3.27	Average
Grand Mean	3.44	Average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 – 5.15, High,

5.16 -5.98 = Very High. For number 1: 1.00-1.80 = low, 1.81-2.60 = Below average, 2.61-3.40 = Average, 3.41-4.20

High, 4.21 – 5.00 Very high.

Based on the findings in Table 6, the highest mean is from indicator 19 “How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt downhearted and blue?”, with a mean of 3.56, interpreted above average. Sad employees might express that they find their duty to be excessively burdensome or intricate. This may have substantial consequences for both the mental health of employees and the overall dynamics of the job setting (DelTienne,2020). And the lowest mean is from indicator 36 “During the past month, how much of the time have you been in low or very low spirits?”, with a mean of 3.27, interpreted as average. Employees believe negatively of their jobs and your organization when morale is low A decrease in employee engagement and commitment to their tasks could result in a reduction in overall productivity. It can negatively impact both the mental health of employees and the performance of the organization (Charaba, 2022). The respondents' depression obtained total mean scores of 3.44, interpreted as having an average depression level.

To support the findings, based on the study of Lerner (2013), having an average level of depression is associated with work absences and decreased work performance, which also partially confirmed that work-related stressors exacerbate this effect. In contrast, depression frequently presents individuals with the opportunity to engage in contemplation and reflection of their lives and life paths, thereby allowing them the chance to create beneficial transformations (Vogel,2021).

The Level of Loss of Behavioral/Emotional Control of Work-From-Home-Employees

Based on the findings in Table 7, the highest mean is from indicator 27 “How often, during the past month, have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?”, with a mean of 3.68, interpreted above average. When negative feelings were prevalent, the organization descended into despair and progressively became less dynamic and stimulating, (Sawyer & Clair, 2022). While the lowest mean is from indicator 28 “During the past month, did you think about taking your own life?”, with a mean of 2.06, interpreted as below average. Employees that are in high workplace stress are thought to be a primary contributor to suicides, particularly when employees face substantial job demands without sufficient Workplace stress is identified as a primary factor contributing to suicides, particularly when employees perceive limited control over demanding job requirements. According to a StressPulse survey, the predominant sources of workplace stress are excessive workload (46%) and interpersonal conflicts (28%). It is noteworthy that a significant proportion of employees who attempt or succumb to suicide often grapple with unaddressed mental health or psychological disorders. (Robinson, 2020).

The respondents' loss of behavioral/emotional control obtained total mean scores of 3.17 interpreted as average loss of behavioral/emotional control.To support the findings in accordance with the study of Georgivia (2023), having an average loss of behavioral/emotional control they will struggle to comprehend and control their emotions may experience elevated levels of tension and diminished job satisfaction. Furthermore, inability to effectively communicate with employees may result in a decrease of trust

and collaboration among leaders. In contrast, having emotional control facilitates the development of stronger interpersonal connections, academic and occupational achievement, and the realization of individual and professional aspirations. Additionally, it can assist you in establishing a connection with your emotions, manifesting your intentions into tangible results, and making well-informed choices regarding what is most significant to you (Segal et al., 2023).

Table 7. *The Level of Loss of Behavioral/Emotional Control*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
8. During the past month, have you had any reason to wonder if you were losing your mind, or losing control over the way you act, talk, think, feel, or of your memory?	3.29	Average
14. During the past month, have you been in firm control of your behavior, thoughts, emotions, or feelings?	3.04	Average
16. During the past month, how often did you feel that you had nothing to look forward to?	3.20	Average
18. How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt emotionally stable?	3.40	Average
20. How often have you felt like crying, during the past month?	3.50	Average
21. During the past month, how often have you felt that others would be better off if you were dead?	2.75	Below Average
24. How often, during the past month, did you feel that nothing turned out for you the way you wanted it to?	3.65	Above average
27. How often, during the past month, have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?	3.68	Above average
28. During the past month, did you think about taking your own life?	2.06	Below average
Grand Mean	3.17	Average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 - 5.15, High, 5.16 -5.98 = Very High. For number 9: 1.00-1.80 = low, 1.81-2.60 = Below average, 2.61-3.40 = Average, 3.41-4.20 High, 4.21 - 5.00 Very high

The Level of General Positive Affect of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 8. *The Level of General Positive Affect*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
4. During the past month, how much of the time have you felt that the future looks hopeful and promising?	3.93	Above average
5. How much of the time, during the past month, has your daily life been full of things that were interesting to you?	3.83	Above average
6. How much of the time, during the past month, did you feel relaxed and free from tension?	3.39	Average
7. During the past month, how much of the time have you generally enjoyed the things you do?	3.66	Above average
12. When you have got up in the morning, this past month, about how often did you expect to have an interesting day?	3.72	Above average
17. How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt calm and peaceful?	3.57	Above average
26. During the past month, how much of the time has living been a wonderful adventure for you?	3.62	Above average
31. How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt cheerful, lighthearted?	3.94	Above average
34. During the past month, how much of the time were you a happy person?	3.85	Above average
37. How often, during the past month, have you been waking up feeling fresh and rested?	3.46	Average
Grand Mean	3.70	Above average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 - 5.15, High, 5.16 -5.98 = Very High.

Based on the findings in Table 8, the highest mean is from indicator 31 “How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt cheerful, lighthearted?”, with a mean of 3.94, interpreted above average. Enthusiasm at work is more probable among contented employees. Their work is more likely to inspire and provide them with a sense of purpose. Enhanced focus and concentration result from this, potentially propelling productivity to new heights (Politte, 2023). And the lowest mean is from indicator 6 “How much of the time, during the past month, did you feel relaxed and free from tension?” with a mean of 3.39, interpreted as average. As employees' enthusiasm for their work decreases their propensity to express their views and thoughts gradually diminishes. Typically, this is because they are endeavoring to distance themselves from the organization and no longer share its enthusiasm for success (Persin, 2022).

The respondents' general positive affect obtained total mean scores of 3.70, interpreted as having an average general positive affect level. To support the findings based on the findings of Lin et al., (2016), An employee's positive affect may have had a direct influence on both the standard of job performance and well-being. Additionally, Individual job fit may have had a direct impact on the quality of job performance, and well-being may have had an indirect impact on the quality of job performance. In contrast, negative affects include perceiving the world in a more depressing manner, having negative emotions, and being surrounded by more negativity in both relationships and environment (Scott,2022).

The Level of Emotional Ties of Work-From-Home Employees

Table 9. *The Level of Emotional Ties*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
10. During the past month, how much of the time have you felt loved and wanted?	3.92	Above average
23. How much of the time, during the past month, did you feel that your love relationships, loving and being loved, were full and complete?	3.88	Above average
Grand Mean	3.90	Above average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 – 5.15, High, 5.16 -5.98 = Very High.

Based on the findings in Table 9, the highest mean is from indicator 10, with a mean of 3.92, interpreted above average. Positive mental health in the workplace facilitates the adaptability of teams during responsibility and role changes. It ultimately enables every person to achieve their utmost capabilities, (Perry, 2022). While the lowest mean is from indicator 23 “How much of the time, during the past month, did you feel that your love relationships, loving and being loved, were full and complete?”, with a mean of 3.88, interpreted as above average. Strong familial bonds furnish essential social support, which has the potential to relieve psychological challenges such as isolation and anxiety. Family relationships were enhanced by work-from-home by means of appropriate adaptive processes. A positive correlation existed between work-from-home and time spent with family (Wu et al., 2022). The respondents' emotional ties obtained total mean scores of 3.90.

To support the findings, having above average increases retention, and productivity. Furthermore, an increase in employee engagement with their work and the organization will eventually manifest in improved work quality. However, emotions are intricate and challenging to define, (Dorrington, 2018). However, A notable decrease in productivity ensues when employees lack emotional ties to their employer. inevitably, teams that perform poorly appear to be most adversely affected by the absence of an emotional connection, (Sharma, 2022).

The Level of Life Satisfaction of Work-From-Home Employees

Based on the findings in Table 10, The work-from-home employees' life satisfaction obtained total mean scores of 3.57, interpreted as having an above average life satisfaction. Employees that can work from home increase their happiness at work and it correlates to overall life happiness (Robinson, 2022).

Table 10. *The Level of Life Satisfaction*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. How happy, satisfied, or pleased have you been with your personal life during the past month?	3.96	Above average
Grand Mean	3.96	Above average

Legend 1.00-1.83 = Low, 1.84-2.66 = Below Average, 2.67-3.49 = Average, 3.50-4.32 Above average, 4.33 – 5.15, High, 5.16 -5.98 = Very High.

To support the findings having an above average life satisfaction can contribute to favorable concrete results, including heightened engagement in work-related matters, reduced emotional exhaustion, increased peace of mind, enhance). While in colleagues, and increased work participation (Merkin, 2020). While those employees who are dissatisfied with their life will likely experience personal sadness, and overall dissatisfaction will hinder them from attaining fulfillment in their jobs, (Demirel, 2014)

Table 11. *The summary of Mental Health*

Domains	Mean	Interpretation
Anxiety	3.56	Above average
Depression	3.44	Average
Loss of Behavioral/Emotional Control	3.17	Average
General Positive Affect	3.70	Above average
Emotional Ties	3.90	Above average
Life Satisfaction	3.96	Above average
Grand Mean	3.62	Above average

To support the findings according to the study of Perry (2022), positive mental health in the workplace facilitates the adaptability of organizations during responsibility and role changes. Not to mention confronting enormous challenges. It assists employees in flourishing in their positions, coping with tension, and enhancing resilience. It ultimately enables every employee to achieve their highest capabilities. In contrast based on the study of Eys (2021), employees experience challenges with concentration, meeting

deadlines, and utilizing their creative abilities when confronted with job-related tension. Stress has the potential to initiate various mental health issues, such as exhaustion, anxiety, depression, and conflict, which can have a substantial negative effect on job productivity.

The Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Mental Health of Work-From-Home employees.

Table 12. *The Correlation of Self-Efficacy and Mental Health*

Variables	r	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Self-Efficacy And Mental Health	.24	.005	Reject the Hypothesis	Statistically Significant

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

The relationship between self -efficacy and Mental health is shown in Table 12. There is a very low correlation between self-eficacy and mental health ($r=.24$), and the relationship is significant ($p= .005$). The null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically significant relationship between self-eficacy and mental health of work-from-home employees.

To support these findings, the study of Ocel (2016), the findings reveal that there is a positive correlation between self-eficacy and mental health. Additionally, the results indicate that the mental health of employees with high levels of self-eficacy is enhanced when they collaborate with supportive leaders. When managers or leaders permit employees to exercise creativity while performing their duties, it improves the psychological well-being of the employees. Employees who possess a strong psychological well-being may find it more advantageous to manage work-related challenges and family-work conflicts. In contrast, in the study of Mata and Tarroja (2022), Despite the absence of self-eficacy as a moderating variable, employees reported a high level of mental health. Self-eficacy and emotional fatigue are distinct factors that influence mental health. The findings suggest that there is no correlation between mental health and self-eficacy; therefore, self-eficacy does not weaken. Even if someone has high self-eficacy, they may still experience emotional exhaustion, and this can still affect their overall psychological well-being. In accordance with the findings.

The Relationship of Job Satisfaction and Mental Health of Work-From-Home employees

Table 13. *The Correlation of Job Satisfaction and Mental Health*

Variables	r	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Job Satisfaction And Mental Health	.12	.164	Accept the Hypothesis	Statistically not Significant

**Correlation is not significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

The relationship between job satisfaction and mental health is shown in Table 13. There is a very low correlation between job satisfaction and mental health ($r=.12$), and the relationship is not significant ($p= .164$). The null hypothesis was accepted, indicating a statistically not significant relationship between job satisfaction and mental health of work-from-home employees.

To support the findings, according to Otaghi et al. (2023), there is no correlation between job satisfaction and mental health. A plausible hypothesis for this absence of correlation is that job satisfaction could be impacted by an assortment of variables that are not associated with mental health. An individual may experience job satisfaction, for instance, if they derive enjoyment from their work or if they receive competitive compensation. However, it is not guaranteed that such factors will necessarily exert an influence on their mental health. In contrast, Bergefurt et al. (2021), there is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and mental health. The results of the study indicate that working from home employees' sleep quality, mood, tension, and fatigue are influenced by their level of job satisfaction.

Qualitative Phase

Thematic Analysis

Table 14. *The Thematic Analysis*

Superordinate Themes	Subthemes
Thriving From Home	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beyond the New Normal Stress Proof Professionalism Technical Trials
The workplace revolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No More Traffic Jams Maximizing Productivity in my pajamas When regular work hours become 24/7
Adapt and Thrive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Time Clarity in the Chaos Inhale, Exhale

This section discusses the emerged themes and categories derived from one-on-one interviews. It delves into the analysis and interpretation of the participants' and researchers' perspectives on the experiences associated with the phenomena under investigation.

The tables show the themes emerged from the significant statements of work-from-home employees about their lived experiences, challenges and coping mechanism.

Thriving From Home

Employees who work-from-home concurred that they had achieved significantly more productive and task-oriented work without encountering any disruptions because of consistent office-based employee communication. Employees became more practical and cautious in their interactions; they sought one another only when it was necessary; and they attained a greater degree of autonomy in attempting to resolve minor issues on their own. The employees' digital proficiencies experienced significant growth because of the novel challenges. They were introduced to and acquired knowledge of previously irrelevant tools, while the technical foundation was provided within the office environment. Work execution became more convenient by eliminating the need for travel, day-to-day organization became simpler, and an initial balance between work and personal life was established. Additionally, they emphasized that they conducted work processes through meetings that were more efficient and required less time for lengthy discussions (Kovacs & Kalman, 2022).

Beyond The New Normal

The predominant issue stated by work-from-home is the experience of loneliness and isolation, which can have broader impacts beyond the individual affected. Certain indicators of isolation include higher levels of stress and decreased decision-making abilities. These attributes are of significance to employers when considering individuals who hold significant responsibilities. Unfortunately, the state of isolation further complicates the task of employers to recognize these signs (Modi, 2019).

These sub themes highlights the isolation nature of work-from-home. Specifically, participant 4 talked about the struggle of being isolated in work-from-home set-up.

“Since isolated nga at walang makausap. Wala kang makakulitan na friends iba kase talaga kapag on site din talgang buhay na buhay ka. Pero kapag work from home minsan nakakatulog ka dahil walang kausap at nagkakaroon ka ng Overtime, idle, over break.” (Since it's isolated, and there's no one to talk to, you don't have friends to annoy, unlike when you're on-site, where you're really lively. But when you work from home, sometimes you fall asleep because there's no one to talk to, and you end up having overtime, being idle, or taking extra breaks).

Stress-Proof Professionalism

Like the process of forming new routines, attaining, and sustaining a harmonious balance between professional and familial obligations necessitates substantial investment of time and commitment. Occasionally, you may devote more time to one activity than the other, but the objective is to discover a harmonious balance that optimizes your functioning (Herrity, 2023).

These sub themes pointed out that employees who have the option to work from home have to set boundaries between their work and their family life. Specifically, participant 3 talked about how he handles his work and personal life.

“Kapag working hours hindi ko hinahalo yung stress ko sa family or iba pang aspeto professionalism lang din. Kase mawawala ako sa focus non, tsaka para mafocus ako hindi ako madalas mag social media lalo kapag may pasok pa ako at nakatutok sa monitor.” (During working hours, I don't let my stress affect my family or other aspects of my life; I maintain professionalism. If I let it affect them, I'll lose focus. To stay focused, I try not to use social media frequently, especially when I have work and I'm focused on my monitor.)

Technical Trials

Technical issues that limit productivity are a common challenge for individuals who work from home. One of the most significant challenges is inconsistent internet connections, which can disrupt video conferences and cause delays in sending and receiving emails. This can be especially problematic for individuals who rely on the internet for their work, such as graphic designers, web developers, or content creators. Technical issues can be a significant challenge for individuals who work from home (Chen, 2022).

These sub themes underscore one of the major challenges of work-from-home employees is technical problems such as slow internet connections and loss of power electricity. Specifically, participant 4 talked about the struggle of being a work-from-home employee.

Nawalan ng kuryente since umuulan may shortage sa kuryente so ayon ayaw talaga bumukas lahat. Ayun nagkaron yon ng epekto sa sa work performance ko sympre nawawala ko sa focus kapag ganun at nasstress din ako kapag antagal tagal bumalik. So todo contact agad TL ko pero maayos naman. Tapos minsan nawawalan ng internet kapag di mo naagapan pwedeng kalahati lang yung sahudin mo. (We lost power because of the rain, and there was an electricity shortage, so nothing really worked. That has an impact on my work performance. Of course, I lose focus when that happens, and I also get stressed when it takes a long time to come back. I immediately contacted my Team Leader, but everything was fine. Sometimes, we lose internet, and if you don't address it promptly, you might only receive half of your salary).

Similarly, participant 14 talked about the struggle of being a work-from-home employee because of the environmental noises. The participants said “During work may sumasabay na nagpapatugtog ng malakas tapos minsan hindi mapakiusapan. Hindi ka makapagfocus sa ginagawa mo kaya minsan late kong napapasa yung mga task na binibigay.” (During work, there's someone who plays music loudly, and sometimes, they can't be reasoned with. It's hard to focus on what you're doing, so sometimes, I end up submitting my tasks late).

To support the findings, a study conducted by Steelcase demonstrates that employees may have difficulty concentrating in a loud workplace, which can reduce their average "productive" time by 86 minutes. Working-from-home employees are exposed to a variety of sounds that are distinct to each environment. As an individual with mild hearing who resides in a close area to an active home construction site and contends with a worn-out air conditioning unit that produces loud trilling sounds, the absence of noise has transformed into a minor inconvenience ever since they began working-from-home, (Ramaweda,2021).

The Workplace Revolution

The popularity of telecommuting is increasing among employees and employers, with a recent survey showing that 86% of managers believe that work-from-home is the future. The hybrid work model, which allows employees to work both work-from-home and in the office, has become a popular approach that accommodates employees' need for flexibility. Employees prefer the hybrid remote-office work setup, with 59% of them choosing it. Adopting this approach can prioritize employee well-being, improve job satisfaction, work-life balance, and increase productivity (Bandapixel,2023).

No More Traffic Jams

Based on the study of work-from-home represents an important transition, particularly for employees accustomed to operating entirely from an actual workplace. It can be difficult, isolating, overwhelming, and distressing, among other things. Nevertheless, let's confront it. Everybody despises spending two to two and a half hours per day commuting in crowded morning and evening traffic. It negatively impacts one's health. One's health may be negatively impacted by navigating through traffic, inhaling exhaust pollutants, and distressing over being late to work. Even though it's not ideal to spend eight hours a day tethered to your office in isolation while working from home, it's a better existence because you have more time to spend with your loved ones (Sinha, 2023).

These sub themes highlight one of the benefits associated with work-from-home employees is the increased flexibility that comes with their schedules. They are not required to commute every day. Specifically, participant 7 talked about the advantage of being a work-from-home employee.

“Pag work-from-home ka kase very convenient kasi nasa bahay kalang unlike yung nasa on site ka before kase naka on site ako very time consuming yung nag tatravel kapa since qc pa yung work ko before so 1hr 30 mins yung travel ko depende sa traffics very convenient yung work-from-home kase gumigising lang ako tapos mag wwork na ko unlike yung pag on site mag aayos kapa tapos babyahe kapa.” (Working from home is very convenient because you're at home, unlike when I used to work on-site. It was very time-consuming to travel to my workplace since it was in Quezon City, and my travel time was about 1 hour and 30 minutes, depending on traffic. Working from home is very convenient because I can simply wake up and start working, unlike when working on-site when you have to get ready and commute).

Maximizing Productivity in My Pajamas

Employees productivity is positively correlated with work-from-home arrangements, according to the findings. Additionally, work-life balance is discovered to be a substantial mediator between work-from-home arrangements and employee productivity. In the same way, the outcome demonstrated that time/schedule flexibility mediates considerably between work-from-home arrangements and employee productivity (Diaz et al., 2023).

These sub themes pointed out employees who have the option to work from home and maintain a healthy work-life balance tend to be more productive, as they have the ability to adjust their schedules and work during non-traditional hours. Specifically participants 3 he talked about how he maximizes his daily routine.

Ang daily routine ko is gumising ng maaga. Tapos ginagawa ko muna yung mga responsibilities ko sa bahay. Tapos let's say 20 minutes before mag start ang working hours ko. Then sa bahay lang naman ako so kahit half lang din yung uniform basta yung taas pang uniform talaga. Kase required ang pagsuot sa amin ng uniform. Then kapag working hours na syempre doon lang ako sa area ko bawal ang manggulo sa akin kase nadidistract ako. Tapos ano pa ba? Hmmm... Basta may coffee lang sa lamesa ko ayos na yon. (My daily routine is to wake up early. Then, I attend to my household responsibilities first. Let's say 20 minutes before my working hours start. Since I work from home, I can wear just the top half of my uniform as long as the upper part is the actual uniform, as wearing it is a requirement. When it's working hours, I stay in my designated area because I get distracted when people disturb me. Also, as long as there's coffee on my table, I'm good.)

Additionally, Participant 15's perspective provides insight into how work-from-home can enhance their work-life balance. He said that “Advantage naman sya kase nababalance ko ang work life balance kase nasa bahay lang pwede na ko makipag bonding sa mga pamilya ko or friends kaya nagiging advantage compare sa on site matagal ka pa makakauwi.” (It's an advantage because I can balance my work-life effectively. I can stay at home and easily bond with my family or friends, which is an advantage compared to being on-site where

it takes a long time to get back home).

The results contribute to the greater comprehension of family relationships and WFH. A positive correlation existed between WFH and time spent with family. In addition to affecting work and daily life, working from home has an effect on relationships with family members. Family relationships were enhanced by work-from-home via appropriate adaptive processes (Wu et al., 2022).

When Regular Work Hours becomes 24/7

Work-related pressures are a leading cause of poor mental health. The variety of stressors reported by employees highlights the severity and complexity of their work conditions, including unexpected workloads, shifting deadlines, and increased work. The problem arises when additional work is assigned to employees who are already burdened with work. Work-from-home environments also affect work schedules (Memon et al., 2022).

Sub themes underscore the unexpected work, shifting and schedules of work-from-home employees. Specifically, participant 1 talked about how his work becomes 24/7.

“Mayroong pangyayare na ganyan noong birthday ng anak ko. Dahil nga sa bahay lang ang work ko edi kampante ako na magagawa ko yung ibang gawain dahil birthday ng anak ko, tulad ng pagluluto kase may handa tsaka tapos na yung shift ko. So ayun, during the birthday celebration biglang tumawag ang superbisor namin at agaran akong pinapasok sa zoom meeting. Kaya sa buong hapon ng selebrasyon wala ako at nakakalungkot lang ang pangyayare na iyon kase may okasyon at biglaang patawag sa akin kaya kailangan ko makisama at gawin yun.” (Something like that happened on my child's birthday. Because my work is at home, I was confident that I could manage other tasks on my child's birthday, such as cooking because we had a celebration, and I had already finished my shift hours. So, during the birthday celebration, our supervisor suddenly called, and I immediately joined the zoom meeting. So, for the entire afternoon of the celebration, I was absent, and it was just a sad turn of events because it was a special occasion, and I had to go due to an unexpected call).

Similarly, participant 14 talked about the struggle of being a work-from-home employee because of the environmental noises. The respondents 6 said *“If ever tapos na yung duty ko biglaan na lang may papagawa kahit tapos na and di naman kadalasan nababayaran yung overtime ko. Parang extended ang trabaho ko dahil nga nasa bahay lang ako parang one call away dapat ako sa kanila.”* (If ever my shift is over, there are sudden tasks assigned even though I've already finished, and my overtime is not often compensated. It's like my work gets extended because I'm at home, and it's as if I should always be one call away from them).

To support the escalating issue of overwork has been caused by work-from-home and additional factors that have contributed to a significant number of employees working extended hours. Before employees learn to limit their excessive hours of work, we cannot genuinely prioritize their well-being. If they were just a tiny workload for the additional hours worked throughout the pandemic would be of lesser concern. Still, excessive workloads have been a persistent issue. Since 2000, an extensive increase in health threats can be traced back to extended work hours, according to a study recently published by the World Health Organization (Beheshti, 2021),

Adapt and Thrive

Employees who work from home during the pandemic experienced two types of stress: first, stress related to the work itself and the pressure to perform better in an unsuitable environment; second, stress caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Although employees implemented coping mechanisms to manage tension, these measures may not have been effective for all staff members, as certain individuals were more adversely affected due to their inability to perform their duties efficiently while remotely. As means of enhancing their mental well-being, employees implemented a range of coping mechanism: developing optimism, seeking social support, engaging in physical exercise, independently resolving telework challenges, putting in additional hours of work, and intentionally avoiding phone calls (Kokuntensa, 2021).

Quality Time

Beyond being beneficial for health and relationships, ensuring that your employees maintain a healthy work-life balance can also increase their performance and productivity. In essence, employees will exhibit greater effort, commit to fewer errors, and potentially serve as brand advocates if they do not perceive their work as a burden, (Wedgwood, 2022).

Sub themes underscore how work-from-home employees cope with their social life. Specifically, participant 8 talked how he will connect with their friends and family in order to maintain a social life and reduce stress.

“Nakikipag bonding na lang ako sa mga kaibigan o family ko after ko magwork laro laro ganun para makapag relax din at magkaroon ng social life at para mawala din stress ko.” (I just bond with my friends or my family after work and play games like that, so I can also relax, have a social life, and relieve my stress).

Clarity in the Chaos

Maintaining calmness facilitates rational thought and enables one to arrive at sensible decisions. When confronting difficulties, mental clarity is of the utmost importance. Clarity will facilitate the logical and effortless processing of solutions when the mind is at ease and unburdened (Dos Santos, 2021).

Sub themes highlight how work-from-home employees handle their stress. Specifically, participant 1 talked about how he will choose to stay calm and not make regrettable decisions.

“Ang ginagawa ko lang kapag may mga ganitong pangyayare sa akin kinakalma ko muna sarili ko para kahit paano hindi ako makagawa ng mga desisyon na sa tingin kong magsisisi ako sa huli. Kapag naman sa tingin ko gulong gulo na ako humihinto ako saglit tapos ipapahinga ko saglit sarili ko para makapag recharge ng sarili.” (The only thing I do when things like this happen to me is to calm myself first so that somehow, I don't make decisions that I think I'll regret in the end. When I think I'm in a mess, I stop for a while and then I rest for a while to recharge myself).

Additionally, participants 2, how she manages her colleagues who are causing her to become frustrated. *“Kapag nagagalit na ako umaalis muna ako okaya naglilibang muna para mawala sa isip ko yung galit, kinakalma ko yung sarili ko para hindi lumaki yung gulo. Actually, mababait naman yung mga katrabaho ko may times lang talaga na hindi maiiwasan at makaka encounter ka ng pagtatalo pero nauuwi din sa pagkakaayos. Kinakausap ko sila thru chats kase madalang lang kami magkita sa working hours naming kapag nagkakabonding naman kami duon kami nagoopen up sa isa't isa.”* (When I'm upset, I leave first, unwind first to release the tension, and then I calm myself, so the matter doesn't escalate. My coworkers are actually quite nice; sometimes disagreements are inevitable and must be resolved, but otherwise, things go well. We aren't often seen together during working hours, so I connect with them via chats. and we open to one another when we get together to bond).

To support these findings based on the study of Dos Santos (2021), maintaining control enables one to engage in discussions without the risk of conflict. Maintaining calm will enable you to engage in discussions regarding issues with comfort and trust. One must approach problems with patience. Engaging in combat or unwarranted disagreements will not yield a resolution to the issue at hand and may engender feelings of frustration and irritation among all parties involved.

Inhale, exhale

Irregular and shallow breathing is common when feeling stressed or anxious. Deep breathing, also known as diaphragmatic breathing, allows for more air flow and can reduce stress and anxiety, improve attention span, and lower pain levels. This technique is beneficial because it allows for more air to enter the body and promotes a sense of calmness (Princing, 2021).

The sub themes underscore how work-from-home employees use breathing exercise to relieve stress. Specifically, participant 15 talked about how breathing exercise calms his mind.

“Kapag may problema naman akong kinakaharap sa work ginagawa ko lang yung breathing exercise para mawala kahit papano at di ako gaanong maapektuhan” (When I encounter problems at work, I simply do the breathing exercise to make them go away, even if only a little, and not be too affected)

Integration of findings

Integration of QUANTITATIVE-QUALITATIVE data for Self-Efficacy

Table 15. Integration of data for Self-Efficacy

Quantitative	Qualitative (Thriving from home theme)	Integrated Theme Key Priority Areas
The quantitative analysis, using the general self-efficacy scale (GSE), reveals that work-from home-employee tend to have high self-efficacy with a mean score of 3.17 (high).	The employees who work- from-home express happiness with their current arrangement. It optimizes their time and enhances self-efficacy. Social isolation is one of <u>employees'</u> problem regarding this new set-up. Additionally, Technical issues such as poor internet connections, power outages, and environmental sounds affect employee's self-efficacy.	The integrated theme suggests that work-from-home employees are facing a new struggle that only arises on work-from-home set-up. A key priority is to have a training webinar to have proficiency in diagnosing and resolving typical technical issues that may arise within the context of a home office environment. Additionally, methods and strategies for mitigating the effects of environmental disturbances <u>in order to</u> maintain a peaceful and concentrated work environment

Based on the integrated results of QUANTATIVE-QUALITATIVE state that despite the work-from-home employee possessing a high level of self-efficacy, However, as their work is heavily reliant on a consistent electricity supply and reliable access to the internet, new difficulties arise. On certain days, they encounter internet connectivity issues that hinder the smooth completion of their tasks. Additionally, their tension levels are heightened by unanticipated power outages that occur on particular times, considering the complex nature of their work which relies on computer-based systems. Additionally, the disruptive effects of the unwanted noises arising from their environments further impede their capacity to focus on their tasks. Their inability to concentrate is made difficult by these problems, which negatively impacts the efficiency and output of their duties.

To support the findings, technical issues that limit productivity are a common challenge for individuals who work from home. One of

the most significant challenges is inconsistent internet connections, which can disrupt video conferences and cause delays in sending and receiving emails. Technical issues can be a significant challenge for individuals who work from home, (Chen, 2022). Moreover, working-from-home employees are exposed to a variety of sounds that are distinct to each environment. A study conducted by Steelcase demonstrates that employees may have difficulty concentrating in a loud workplace, which can reduce their average "productive" time by 86 minutes, (Ramaweda,2021)

Potentially addressing this issue, the company may create a webinar that ensures that it addresses the new problems that arise during the work-from-home environment. This includes optimizing Internet Connectivity, technical troubleshooting Q&A, and noise management techniques. The primary objective of the webinar is to provide those working from home with the necessary knowledge and abilities to effectively navigate the technical components of work-from-home.

Integration of QUANTITATIVE -QUALITATIVE data for Job Satisfaction

Table 16. Integration of data for Job Satisfaction

Quantitative	Qualitative (Digital renaissance)	Integrated Theme Key Priority Areas
The quantitative analysis, using the Minnesota job satisfaction (MSQ), reveals that work-from home-employee tend to have high job satisfaction with a mean score of 3.79 (high).	The work-from-home arrangement is highly advantageous for numerous employees due to its time flexibility, allowing them the opportunity to maintain a more harmonious work-life balance. Nevertheless, employees may also encounter the challenge of unanticipated additional work demands that extend beyond their designated shifts.	The integrated theme suggests that work-from-home employees. struggle with post-shift work obligations. The key priority is to promote open communication regarding workload and deadlines between employees and supervisors. Clarify whether employees are obligated to provide advance notice over overtime work and specify the conditions under which brief notice may be permitted.

As a result of the integration of QUANTITATIVE-QUALITATIVE data for job satisfaction it is found that job satisfaction of work-from-home employees is high. However, a significant challenge that emerges is the presence of unanticipated added workloads that frequently exceed the boundaries of the employees' scheduled work periods. Although flexibility offers numerous advantages, the loss of boundaries between work and personal life may result in a greater burden, which may have a negative impact on achieving the ideal balance between the two.

To support the findings based on Beheshti (2021), the escalating issue of overwork has been caused by work-from-home and additional factors that have contributed to a significant number of employees working extended hours.

Companies can foster a more collaborative and transparent atmosphere at work by encouraging open communication and establishing explicit guidelines concerning overtime labor. This approach not only facilitates efficient workload management but also ultimately enhances employee satisfaction and well-being.

Integration of QUANTITATIVE -QUALITATIVE data for Mental Health

Table 17. Integration of data for Mental Health

Quantitative	Qualitative (Cultivating resilience)	Integrated Theme Key Priority Areas
The quantitative analysis, using the mental health inventory 38 (MHI-38), reveals that work-from home-employee tend to have average mental health with a mean score of 3.50 (Above average).	Work-from-home employees employ a coping mechanism when confronted with challenges in their work, which involves maintaining composure through the practice of controlled breathing exercises Through the intentional execution of controlled breathing exercises, individuals have the capacity to boost their emotional regulation and nurture a more productive and composed attitude when addressing challenges. Consequently, this can lead to enhanced work performance and mental well-being.	The integrated theme suggests that work-from-home employees should learn about breathing exercises as it enhances their ability to regulate their emotions. A key priority is to Organize a breathing training seminar. As well as recognizing problems may stress employees. Lastly Provide mental health resources, counseling, and stress management programs to boost employee well-being.

The results of QUANTITATIVE-QUALITATIVE data for mental health reveal that indicates an above-average level of mental well-being. This positive outcome is attributed to the effective coping mechanisms employed by individuals to navigate the challenges inherent in the work-from-home environment. Work-from-home employees employ controlled breathing exercises as a coping

mechanism, enabling them to maintain composure when facing work-related challenges. Through intentional execution of these exercises, individuals enhance emotional regulation, fostering a more productive and composed attitude. This proactive approach not only contributes to improved work performance but also positively influences mental well-being, creating a harmonious and resilient work-from-home experience.

To support the findings, deep breathing, also known as diaphragmatic breathing, allows for more air flow and can reduce stress and anxiety, improve attention span, and lower pain levels. This technique is beneficial because it allows for more air to enter the body and promotes a sense of calmness, (Princing, 2021).

In response to the integrated theme emphasizing the benefits of breathing exercises for emotional regulation among work-from-home employees, a key priority is organizing a targeted breathing training seminar. This seminar aims to equip employees with practical techniques to enhance emotional well-being and resilience. Acknowledging that unrecognized challenges may induce stress, the webinar will highlight the importance of problem recognition for proactive solutions. Furthermore, the initiative includes providing essential mental health resources, counseling services, and stress management programs to create a supportive framework for employees, ultimately fostering a holistic approach to boost their overall well-being. Participating in this comprehensive webinar can empower employees with valuable tools and resources to navigate the unique challenges of remote work while promoting a positive and resilient mental health environment.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from this study highlights that work-from-home employees exhibit a high level of self-efficacy and an above-average general job satisfaction. The findings indicate a positive state of mental health among these employees, as reflected by an above-average mental health index, and reveal a significant correlation between self-efficacy and mental health. Interestingly, the study found no significant correlation between mental health and job satisfaction among participants. Employees perceive their flexible work environment as beneficial for their mental health and work-life balance. The reduction in commuting leads to financial savings and increased time efficiency. Despite these benefits, participants face challenges such as excessive responsibilities, technical problems, and external noise. Most participants frequently use mindfulness techniques, including social connections with family and friends and deep breathing exercises, as essential coping mechanisms to preserve their mental health.

The study recommends that human resources management implement the Harmony at Home webinar program to support work-from-home employees. This program should focus on enhancing skills pertinent to the work-from-home setup, thereby boosting employees' self-efficacy. Introducing flexible work schedules can further improve job satisfaction by allowing employees to align their work with personal needs. Regular monthly mental health surveys are advised to monitor and address stress-related issues. Comprehensive seminars on self-efficacy and mental health awareness, covering topics like stress management and emotional intelligence, should be conducted. Future researchers are encouraged to reassess the relationship between job satisfaction and mental health to identify specific factors impacting workplace mental health. Continued work-from-home options can help companies retain skilled personnel by adapting to modern work dynamics. Supervisors should prioritize workload planning, time management training, and transparent communication. Employees are encouraged to maintain stress-relief routines, with additional techniques from online platforms. The Harmony at Home webinar program can enhance productivity, resilience, and coping mechanisms for work-from-home employees.

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